

Table continued.

Scientific name	SDR value ^b	Scientific name	SDR value ^b
<i>Cyperus haspan</i> L.	0.422	<i>Paspalum conjugatum</i> Berg.	0.185
<i>Hemarthria compressa</i> (L. f.) R. Br.	0.398	<i>Fimbristylis dichotoma</i> (L.) Vahl	0.151
<i>Phyllanthus virgatus</i> Forst. f.	0.378	<i>Eclipta prostrata</i> (L.) L.	0.132
<i>Euphorbia hirta</i> L.	0.336	<i>Mollugo pentaphylla</i> L.	0.112
<i>Phyla nodiflora</i> (L.) Greene	0.314	<i>Cyperus brevifolius</i> (Rottb.) Hassk.	0.112
<i>Marsilea quadrifolia</i> L.	0.228	<i>Scoparia dulcis</i> L.	0.112
<i>Eragrostis unioides</i> (Retz.) Nees ex Steud.	0.218	<i>Brachiaria murica</i> (Forsk.) Stapf.	0.092
<i>Digitaria ciliaris</i> (Retz.) Koel	0.197	<i>Euphorbia hypericifolia</i> L.	0.069

^aFloating leaf species. ^bMean ratio of relative density and relative frequency.

leaf weed. *Eriocaulon cinereum* showed a submerged life form in early rice growth stages.

For each species, we determined the summed dominance ratio (SDR)—the average of relative density plus relative

frequency. Seven locations were selected randomly and 10 quadrats in each location were temporarily positioned. Species were counted in 70 one-m² quadrats. On the basis of higher SDR value, *Eleocharis atropurpurea*, *Monochoria vaginalis*, *Echinochloa colona*, *Ludwigia perennis*, *Cynodon dactylon*, *Fimbristylis miliacea*, *Rotala indica*, *Sagittaria guayanensis*, *Alternanthera sessilis*, and *Sphenoclea zeylanica* were the most commonly occurring weeds. ■

Water management

Irrigation methods for rice in tropical Australia

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Water is the largest single cost for irrigated dry seeded rice production in north Queensland, Australia. It accounts for about 40% of all variable costs. We evaluated increasing water-use efficiency by

- reducing water use while maintaining grain yield,
- increasing grain yield, while maintaining water use.

The experiment was conducted at Millaroo Research Station (19° 30' S, 147° 30' E) in 1989 dry season (winter). Traditional, intermittent irrigation to the 3-leaf stage, followed by permanent flood

(PF-3L), flooding at sowing (PF-S), flooding at panicle initiation (PF-PI), saturated soil culture (SSC), and intermittent irrigation (II) were compared. SSC is a technique recently developed for soybean: plants are grown on 1.5-m raised beds with water maintained in the furrows between beds, some 10-15 cm below the bed surface. II plots were irrigated by raising the water table to the surface at 7-d intervals. Irrigation treatments were in 288-m² plots replicated three times. Rice cultivar Lemont was used.

Rice yields were 8-9 t/ha in all treatments except II, which yielded 5.4 t/ha (see table). PF-PI and SSC did not reduce grain yield significantly. However, water use of PF-PI (12.1 million liters/ha and SSC (9.4 million liters/ha) was significantly less (P < 0.01) than that of PF-3L (13.7 million liters/ha). Most importantly, water-use efficiency (grain yield per unit consumption of water) of SSC (0.84 t/million liters) was significantly higher than that of PF-3L (0.65 t/million liters).

SSC used up to 1/3 less water than the flooded treatments because evaporation from the saturated soil surface was significantly less than that from a free water surface throughout crop growth. It should be noted that the cultivar used was developed for flooded rice production. The possibility exists that cultivars with improved yield under saturated soil can be developed. ■

Evaluation of drain performance based on head loss fraction in rice-growing acid-saline tract of Kuttanad

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Irrigated rice is the main crop in the acid-saline tract (Kari soils) of Kuttanad in Kerala. Because field elevation (0.5 to 1.5 m below sea level) is much lower than that of the surrounding water bodies, field preparation involves forming a ring bund and draining from inside. Pregerminated seeds are sown into puddled soils both wet and dry seasons.

Soils are extremely acidic and contain toxic concentrations of Fe, Al, and organic products. Yields are very low (1.0-1.5 t/ha), even with 100% adoption of high-yielding varieties. The hydraulic gradient created by the higher elevation water bodies brings toxic salts up to the root zone.

To limit that upward movement of salts and other toxic products, we experimented

Grain yield and water use of rice cultivar Lemont grown under 5 irrigation methods at Millaroo Research Station, North Queensland, 1989 dry season.^a

Irrigation treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	Water use ^b (million liters/ha)	Water-use efficiency (t/million liters)	% water ^c saved
Flooding at sowing	9.3 a	14.0 a	0.66 b	0
Intermittent irrigation followed by permanent flood	8.8 ab	13.7 a	0.65 b	
Flooding at panicle initiation	8.4 ab	12.1 b	0.69 ab	12
Saturated soil culture	7.9 b	9.4 c	0.84 a	31
Intermittent irrigation	5.4 c	7.9 d	0.68 ab	42

^aIn a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level. ^bIncludes all irrigation plus rainfall. ^cSavings calculated in relation to PF - 3L.

Table 1. Head loss fraction for PVC and clay drainage pipes in add-saline, low-elevation tract.

Hours after set of drainage	h_e/h_{tot}	
	Slotted PVC pipe	Baked clay pipe
1	0.87	0.25
6	0.80	0.27
12	0.83	0.27
24	0.83	0.28
48	0.88	0.35
72	0.94	0.41

with subsurface drains. PVC pipes with slots 5 cm long and 0.1 cm wide, and baked clay pipes with an effective bell mouth diameter of 15 cm and tail diameter of 12.5 cm were tested. Effective areas of water entry were 162 cm²/m. Performance was measured through head loss fraction: the ratio of entrance head loss (h) to total head (h_{tot}).

Head loss fraction for the clay pipe

Table 2. Monthly variation of pH and EC of irrigation water in the acid-saline soils of Kuttanad (pooled over 1983-88).

	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar
pH	5.4	5.6	4.4	5.2	5.2	5.3	5.4	5.2	5.3	5.2	5.4	6.1
EC	2.7	2.5	2.2	1.2	0.8	1.0	1.0	0.9	1.3	1.0	0.8	0.9

drain was low and its performance moderate (Table 1). PVC slotted pipes give very poor performance, possibly because of inadequate slot size and/or clogging of the slots by iron oxides.

We also measured irrigation water quality for five hydrological years, 1983-88. Water samples were collected from all irrigation sources at weekly intervals and analyzed for pH and EC. The optimum 5.0-6.0 pH for rice occurred in all months except Jun; the optimum EC of 0.8-1.4 dS/m occurred Jul-Mar (Table 2).

These favorable soil chemical properties are attained primarily during the southwest monsoon. ■

Farming systems

Integrated nutrient management in rice - mustard cropping sequence

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We studied the effect of green manure (GM) *Sesbania aculeata*, blue-green algae (BGA), paper mill sludge (PMS), and Udaipur rock phosphate (URP) with urea, single superphosphate (SSP), and muriate of potash (MP) on wet season rice and succeeding dry season mustard in 1988-89.

Soil was sandy loam, acidic, pH 5.5, 0.3% organic C, 0.03% total N, CEC 7.15 cmol/kg, 24 kg available P/ha, and 155 kg available K/ha.

S. aculeata was sown the first week of Jun and fertilized at 13.2 and 22.0 kg P/ha through SSP, and URP, respectively (see table). At 45 d after sowing (DAS), fresh biomass weighing about 10 t/ha (0.68% N fresh weight basis) was incorporated. Rice variety Parijat was transplanted at 15- × 15-cm spacing 5 d after GM incorporation.

PMS (75% CaCO₃) at one-half the lime requirement of 4.5 t CaCO₃ was added 7 d before transplanting rice. P and R were applied as basal. N was applied to rice in three splits.

BGA algal crust at 10 kg/ha was inoculated 7 d after transplanting. N added through BGA at 30 d after inoculation was estimated at 10.9 kg/ha.

Mustard cultivar M27 was sown at 30- × 10-cm spacing in residual soil moisture immediately after rice harvest the first week of Nov. P and K were applied as basal and N was applied in two splits.

Treatments were laid out in a randomized block design with three replications.

Yields with application of PMS + 60-13-25 and 40-9-17 kg NPK/ha (with and without S) to rice and mustard, respectively, were the highest and comparable to that with GM + 13 kg P/ha + 20-0-25 and 40-9-17 kg NPK/ha (see table). The GM treatment saved 40 kg fertilizer N/ha in rice.

Direct and residual effect of BGA on grain yield of both crops were not pronounced. This might be due to low N from BGA in the acidic soil environment with intermittent dry-wet conditions.

Highest net return and cost:benefit ratio were with PMS + 60-13-25 and 40-9-17 kg NPK/ha (without S) and GM + 13 kg P/ha + 20-0-25 and 40-9-17 kg NPK/ha. ■

Effect of biochemical and chemical fertilizers and paper mill sludge on grain yield and economics of rice + mustard. Orissa, India.

Treatment ^a (kg NPK/ha)		Grain yield (t/ha)		Gross return (\$/ha)	Total cost (\$/ha)	Net return (\$/ha)	Benefit: cost ratio
Wet season	Dry season	Rice	Mustard				
60-13-25	40-9-17	2.0	0.7	622.3	355.7	266.6	1.75
60-22 ^b -25	40-0-16	1.9	0.7	626.8	347.0	279.8	1.81
BGA+40-13-25	40-9-17	1.8	0.7	611.1	352.9	258.2	1.73
GM ^c +20-0-25	40-9-17	2.2	0.8	703.8	349.6	354.2	2.01
GM ^c +BFA+0-0-25	40-9-17	1.8	0.8	629.3	347.0	282.3	1.81
GM ^d +20-0-25	40-0-17	2.1	0.8	670.6	340.2	330.4	1.97
PMS+60-13-25	40-9-17	2.3	0.8	714.9	364.5	350.4	1.96
PMS+60-13-25 (-S)	40-9-17 (3) + gypsum	2.2	0.9	768.7	366.5	402.2	2.10
LSD (0.05)		0.2	0.1			50.3	-

^aBGA =blue-green algae. GM = green manuring with *S. aculeata*. Gypsum applied at 250 kg/ha. PMS =paper mill sludge. ^b50% as a single superphosphate and 50% through Udaipur rock phosphate. ^c13 kg P/ha as single superphosphate was applied to *S. aculeata*. ^d22.0 kg P/ha was applied to *S. aculeata* as Udaipur rock phosphate.

ERRATA

New IRRI publications, 16 (2) (Apr 1991), 25. Line 1 should read: *Editing and publication-a training manual*, by I. Montagnes.

C.V. Singh et al. Rice-based intercropping systems by rainfed upland conditions of Chotanagpur plateau. 15 (3) (Jun 1990), 36.

In column 1, the spacings should read "20-, 45-,45-, 45, and 75-cm."

In column 3 of the text and in the last column of the table, "equivalency" should be "equivalent."